

EDUCATIONAL REFORMS IN THE MOVEMENT OF JADIDISM AT THE END OF THE 19TH CENTURY AND THE BEGINNING OF THE 20TH CENTURY**Alijonova Gulnozakhon,**

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Abstract. By the end of the 19th century, the madrasahs of the East, which had been the cradle of science for centuries, rapidly fell into a crisis towards scholastic views. By this century, while the industrialized science and technology revolution was taking place in Europe, the Muslims of Russia, including Turkestan, were in the middle of the old and new debates. The Jadidism movement spread widely in all regions of the Russian Empire and was distinguished by its comprehensiveness. The educational reforms of this movement gained special importance in the regions of Turkestan and Tatarstan, and the role of this movement in the education system was studied in detail through these regions.

Introduction. The education system for Muslims in the Idyll-Ural region was mainly implemented by mudarris who studied in Bukhara. Naturally, by the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the old school and madrasah system, which could not meet the needs of the times, had to be reformed. For this reason, a group of progressives published articles on their educational reforms in the national press.

Methods. The educational system of old schools and madrasahs in the Idyll-Ural region was adapted to the economic life of the people. For example, students studied at the school-madrassa between October and January and left the madrasah from the beginning of February to the middle of April. Because students helped with agricultural work on hot days. In addition, even in very short lessons, most of the students came to class when they wanted and did not come when they didn't want to. In turn, parents did not take responsibility for their children's education. Such a training system could not give successful results.

Results. Rezauddin ibn Fakhridin spoke about the state of education of students in the region and said: "Children study in schools for seven years. After seven years, it was considered that the children's education was over and they stopped studying. However, some fathers who thought about the fate of their children tried to educate their children themselves.

According to Rezauddin ibn Fakhridin, although children study for seven years, the expected results from education were not positive. The scientist said, "Although I have spent twenty-three years of my life in a madrasa, starting from the age of seven, I have never once sharpened a pencil, why to hold a pencil and how to use it for writing". There was no teacher who looked at my writing and spelling mistakes and corrected them," he cites the reasons for this inefficiency as an example.

Discussion. The curriculum of madrasahs in Orenburg is mainly focused on teaching religious knowledge and morals, and the exact and natural sciences are hardly taught. For example, when the student learns the alphabet in the first year, the surah "Fatiha" is engraved and memorized on a hand-made board. After memorizing this sura, some parts from the book "Shariat al-Iman" were written on the board and memorized to the students. It should be noted that although it is possible to master these lessons in a short time, some students mastered the study within two or three years as a result of the poor and inefficient teaching method in the educational system.

Acknowledgements. In the second stage, some parts of "Haftiyak" were taught. In the third stage, the books "Haftiyak" and "Bedavom" were taught. In the fourth year of Tahsil, books such as "Fazail ash-shuhur" (Virtues of the famous), "Taqiyyun ajab" and "Yusuf wa Zulaikha" were taught. In the fifth year, "Sabot al-ujizin" (Sabotage of the Weak), "Rohati dil" (Pleasure of the Heart), "Miracles", "Nasihah al-Salihiyyin", "Haftiyak Tafsir", "Ustuvani" (The Foundations of Faith book about), lessons were taught from books such as "Boghirkan" and "Saif al-muluk". In the sixth year of education, the teaching of Arabic and Persian languages began. When children develop some recitation, "Forty Hadith", "Shurut as-Salat" (Conditions of Prayer), "A'moli" (Book on Aqeedah), "Ta'allum as-Salat" (Teaching Prayer "worked book"), "Yak al-Kariyat" (One story), "Tuhfatu al-muluk", "Kofiya" (a book on Arabic grammar) and other similar books were taught. In the seventh year of education, lessons from books such as "Majma al-latayif" (Collection of anecdotes), "Kitab al-lubab", "Daqiq al-akhbar" (Source of news), "Hadiya al-suluk", "Nisab al-akhbar" given.

Although other books were taught in some madrasahs instead of the works named above, the above books were used in the educational process in most primary madrasahs in the Idyll-Ural region. However, due to the fact that there were no separate printing presses in the region, the work of providing educational institutions with books was in an extremely difficult situation. This, in turn, led to the deterioration of the quality of lessons in schools.

While living in Bukhara, Marjani developed a program of educational reform, which was

as follows:

1. Subjects taught in madrasahs, such as khasya and Sharh, should be removed from the lesson plans;
2. In madrasahs, such subjects as the Holy Qur'an, hadith, their translations, and the history of Islam should be taught;
3. Do not oppose the teaching of arithmetic, history, geography, medicine, geometry, logic, philosophy and other worldly sciences;
4. Madrasah classes should be reformed based on a specific schedule and procedure.

Since Shahabeddin Marjani studied in Bukhara for the 10th year, he was fully aware of the educational process here. He developed the above reform program as a result of his direct observations. Although his program was strongly opposed by the Emirati elite and a group of clerics, he made a big mark. This can be known from a number of articles published in the national press of Turkestan about Shahabeddin Marjani.

Conclusion. It can be said that Shahabuddin Marjani, Husayn Khan Faizkhani, Qayum Nasiri, Zaynullah Rasuli, Fatih Karimi, Muhammad Zahir Begiev, Rezauddin ibn Fakhridin, Shamsiddin Qultashi, Abdurashid Ibrahim, Ismail Gaspirali, Abdur Auf Fitrat and Mo. The issue of education has always been in the center of attention in the social activities of Minjon Muhammadzhanovs. The progressives of Jadid saw the issue of “maadorisi islah” as a decisive factor for the future fate of the nation.

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